

Georgi Bonchev's paper "Contribution to the springs in Bulgaria", 1939, and its significance for hydrogeology in Bulgaria

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Abstract. In 1939, one of the first summarizing works of the famous Bulgarian geologist Georgi Bonchev "Contribution to the springs in Bulgaria" related to groundwater in the country was published. In his field research, the author visited and described about 60 natural springs or groups of springs with temperatures from 20 °C to over 75 °C, attached to different tectonic zones, over 40 lukewarm and cold springs with mineralized waters and about 290 karst and other cold springs. This article is also relevant for modern hydrogeology. The presented general picture of the locations of the springs, the discharge and qualities of the waters from the natural springs before 1939 allows making comparisons of the occurred changes due to natural and anthropogenic factors.

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INTRODUCTION

Groundwater has been important for the population of Bulgaria from the distant past until now (Antonov and Danchev, 1980; Galabov *et al.*, 1987; Benderev and Stoyanov, 2021). The first hydrogeological investigation in the country, combined with detailed geological studies, began at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century. Most of them were carried out by young and enthusiastic geologists-naturalists who received their education abroad (Borisov, 1981; Mavrudchiev, 2005). One of them was Academician Georgi Bonchev, in whose works related to regional geology, mineralogy and petrography in Bulgaria there is also much information about underground water. The purpose of this paper is to familiarize the modern geological society with this work and to compare some of the data for specific springs presented by G. Bonchev with their current state.

Fig. 1. Academician Georgi Bonchev (August 6, 1866 – March 7, 1955).

ACADEMICIAN GEORGI BONCHEV

Academician Georgi Bonchev (Fig. 1) was born on August 6, 1866, in Zheravna Village (Sliven District, East Bulgaria). He graduated from the Zheravna Primary School in 1876 and the Gabrovo High School in 1888. During 1888–1893, he studied at the University of Zagreb. In 1892, G. Bonchev became a lecturer (still a student) of the course of the deceased Prof. G. Pilar. At his suggestion, the Department of Mineralogy and Petrography was divided into two departments. He received his doctorate after defending two theses with honors.

In 1893, Georgi Bonchev returned to Bulgaria as an extraordinary lecturer in geology, mineralogy and petrography at the Higher School, and in 1895 he became an associate professor at the Department of Mineralogy and Geology at Sofia University. From October 1905 to October 1936, he was full professor and head of the Department of Mineralogy and Petrography. Professor Georgi Bonchev was Dean of the Faculty of Physics and Mathematics four times, and during 1914–1915 he was Rector of Sofia University. Georgi Bonchev was a full member of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences since 1900, founder and first director of the Geological Institute of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (1944–1948), as well as co-founder and first President of the Bulgarian Geological Society (1925). In 1910, Georgi Bonchev compiled a geological map of Bulgaria together with Prof. Georgi Zlatarski.

Georgi Bonchev had a huge scientific production, including more than 140 scientific publications in more than 6000 printed pages, about 180 reports, expert opinions, reviews and others.

THE ARTICLE “CONTRIBUTION TO THE SPRINGS IN BULGARIA”

In 1939, one of the first summarizing works of Georgi Bonchev concerning the groundwater in the country, “Contribution to the springs in Bulgaria,” was published in the journal of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (Fig. 2). In his field research, he visited and described about 60 natural springs or groups of springs with temperatures from 20 °C to >75 °C, attached to different tectonic zones, over 50 lukewarm and cold springs with mineralized waters and about 290 karst and other cold springs. For most of the karst springs, G. Bonchev gave more general information with descriptions of their locations. Only for a small part of them, there are single measurements of their discharge and temperature.

Data for discharge, temperature and chemical composition for some of them are summarized herein (Fig. 3; Tables 1, 2).

DISCUSSION

The presented general picture of the locations of the springs, the discharge and qualities of the waters from the natural springs before 1939 allows making comparisons of the occurred changes due to natural and anthropogenic factors. The most complete information is presented about the natural thermal springs and groups of springs, where significant changes have occurred since 1950 due to drilling in the areas around them (Shterev, 1964, Petrov *et al.*, 1970). As a result, the discharges of the thermal waters in these areas have increased from 1.5 to over 10 times, which has allowed the construction of modern balneological and spa resorts (*e.g.*, Velingrad, Hisar, Strelcha, Sliven, Sandanski). Extraction of water from boreholes from greater depths also leads to higher temperatures compared to natural springs.

The mineral waters in the Rupite area are connected to the youngest volcanic rocks in Bulgaria. The waters spring from sediments in the cold river waters with the release of gases. According to G. Bonchev, there were ~50–60 springs, with an unclear flow rate and different temperature (Fig. 4). In the 1960s, two boreholes with depths of 177 m and 500 m were drilled in the area, which provided hot water on a self-flow basis. In the remaining three drilled boreholes in the area, no significant inflow of warm waters was detected. Due to corrosion of the borehole pipes, in 1980 a new borehole with a depth of 246 m was drilled, which also gives hot water (72 °C) on a self-flow and is the main source of mineral water exploitation at the moment. Currently, the deposit includes three boreholes, one is monitoring, and the flow rate of the other two is a total of 25 l/s. All three boreholes are in extremely poor condition. The Municipality of Petrich commissioned the preparation of a working project for the reconstruction of the boreholes in order to preserve them.

The hottest water discovered by drilling in Bulgaria is at the town of Sapareva Banya (103 °C), with a flow rate of about 14 l/s (Fig. 5), at a temperature in natural springs before 1939 from 42 °C to 86 °C and a total flow rate of only 1.7 l/s. Similar cases of increase in flow rate and temperature after drilling are also found in a number of other deposits of thermal waters (*e.g.*, Beden, Varvara, Velingrad, Pavel Banya).

Приносъ къмъ изворитѣ въ България

(Главно генезисъ и топка)

Отъ проф. д-ръ Г. Бончевъ.
(Докадвано въ Природо-математичния клонъ на 9 мартъ 1937 г.)

Предговоръ

Водната повърхност на терена въ България се състои отъ езера, блата, потоци и рѣки. Водитѣ си тая повърхностъ взема отъ валежитѣ въ страната, водитѣ на които, едни направо, повършно въ тѣхъ се стичатъ, а други посрѣдствено, чрезъ земно просмукване и повършно изтичане презъ извори стигатъ до тѣхъ. Докато първитѣ водни приливи биватъ временни и нетрайни, вторитѣ сж постоянни, и тѣ сж, които хранятъ рѣки и потоци, а чрезъ тѣхъ пълнятъ езерата и блатата.

България, ако и малка страна, но изобилва на извори. Изворитѣ въ нея сж прѣснати въ всички дѣлове на повърхността ѝ и въ всички нейни възможни повършни форми.

Изворнитѣ води въ България сж различни по количество на водитѣ си, по тѣхнитѣ качества, съставъ, физически особности и използване.

По воднитѣ си количества изворнитѣ води сж най-разнообразни: отъ извори съ количество на водитѣ си съ стотици и хиляди литри на минута, съ намаление до десетки и единици, а даже и такива до съзление на водитѣ имъ.

По съставъ изворнитѣ води сж сжщо различни: едни съ изразителенъ минераленъ съставъ, показанъ въ утайкитѣ имъ, въ тѣхнитѣ анализи, тѣхния вкусъ, други съ по-слаба минерализация, която не се проявява въ утайки, вкусъ и мирисъ, а само въ химичната анализа, и трети, въ които и анализата не доказва каква-годе минерализация. Споредъ това и изворнитѣ води у насъ сж: минерални и обикновени изворни води.

Но въ връзка съ състава на изворнитѣ води сж и тѣхнитѣ остали качества като: мирисъ, вкусъ, мжитликъ,

7. Карловска баня. Кота 350. Водитѣ ѝ извиратъ отъ наноси. Тѣ сж нѣколко на брой и съ разни имена:

- а) Банчето, $t^{\circ} 38^{\circ}C$; дебитъ 150 л/м.
- б) Извори извънъ банчето: единъ съ $t^{\circ} 36^{\circ}C$, други 4 съ $t^{\circ} 40^{\circ}C$. Общъ дебитъ 120 л/м.
- в) Парикитѣ нѣколко извора: лѣвъ, дѣсенъ, Кокалчето съ $t^{\circ} 50^{\circ}C$ — $47.5^{\circ}C$. Дебитъ 420 л/м.
- г) Каптажътъ на дветѣ бани; $t^{\circ} 45^{\circ}C$ съ дебитъ 48 л/м. Кота 340 м.

8. Столѣтовски. Извиратъ изъ наноситѣ на р. Стрема. Сега сж каптирани. Основнитѣ имъ скали сж гранитни. $t^{\circ} 34^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 120 л/м. Кота 380 м.

II. На Срдногорската диаклаза сж:

1. Хисарски: Тѣ сж много на брой и всѣки има свое име:

- а) Кюпчезъ съ $t^{\circ} 45^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 51 л/м.
- б) " баня (малкиятъ басейнъ) съ $t^{\circ} 42.5^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 24 л/м.
- в) Инджеза съ $t^{\circ} 42^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 22 л/м.
- г) Чулуджа съ $t^{\circ} 43.5^{\circ}C$ и " 64 л/м.
- д) Хавуза съ $t^{\circ} 48^{\circ}C$ и " 168 л/м.
- е) Гювеча въ Хавуза, $t^{\circ} 41.5^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ малъкъ.
- ж) Чешмата при Инджеза, $t^{\circ} 38^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ до 12 л/м.
- з) Пералията при Инджеза $t^{\circ} 42^{\circ}C$ и " 21 л/м.
- и) Момина баня $t^{\circ} 47^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 374 л/м.
- к) Парикитѣ подъ Момина баня 3 извора: 1 съ $t^{\circ} 40^{\circ}C$, 2 съ $t^{\circ} 45^{\circ}C$ и 3 — $t^{\circ} 49^{\circ}C$.

Общъ дебитъ 328 л/м. (ужъ ги каптираха, но сега колко вода иматъ не е ясно).

- л) Самодивско кладенче при дѣба на Чаиръ-дере. $t^{\circ} 27^{\circ}C$, дебитъ малъкъ.
- м) Пепелешката съ $t^{\circ} 41.6^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 6.5 л/м.
- н) Кална баня (гюльгъ съ $t^{\circ} 41^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 1.4 л/м.).
- о) Чаиръ баня съ $t^{\circ} 45^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ неясенъ, понеже извира изъ рѣчинитѣ пѣсьци.
- п) Спировъ изворъ съ $t^{\circ} 74^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 10 л/м.

р) Два извора подъ Мжитликитѣ: единиятъ съ дебитъ и t° неизмѣримъ, понеже се мѣси съ други води и образува гюлища; другиятъ съ $t^{\circ} 35^{\circ}C$ и слабъ дебитъ.

с) Изворътъ до Велковата воденица съ $t^{\circ} 40^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 30 л/м.

т) Изворитѣ източно отъ дола тамъ съ $t^{\circ} 37.4^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 10.6 л/м.

у) Изворътъ подъ воденицата на западния брѣгъ на дола; но тя е вода просмукана отъ воденичната вода. Кота 350 м.

2. Даваджовско банче. Извира подъ селото изъ пѣносъ. Има t° на водата си $37^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ 170 л/м.

3. Желѣзновски изворъ. $2\frac{1}{2}$ км. си-но отъ селото въ низкото равнище тамъ. Водата му е хладка надъ $20^{\circ}C$, понеже въ нея се влива и почвена студена. Водата извира съ мѣхури. Дебитъ надъ 60 л/м. Около му има и по-слаби изворчета.

4. Красновски извори. Каптирани. Извиратъ изъ наноси — t° на водата 31 — $52.6^{\circ}C$ съ дебитъ до 65 л/м. Кота 360 м.

5. Стрелчески извори. Извиратъ изъ едри гранитови чакълища, но съ основа гранитъ. И тѣ сж каптирани, но въ чакълищата. $t^{\circ} 39.8^{\circ}C$ и дебитъ около 200 л/м. Кота 480 м.

6. Бѣтенска-баня (Панагюрско). Изворитѣ сж до с. Бѣта, зап. страна, по диаклази съ сз-на и юн-на посоки. Тѣ сж нѣколко на брой. Най-многочисленитѣ сж:

Дѣлбока баня съ $t^{\circ} 44^{\circ}C$, Банчето съ $t^{\circ} 41^{\circ}C$ и Кюнеца съ $t^{\circ} 44^{\circ}C$, съ общъ дебитъ 1800 л/м. Западно отъ тѣхъ има още 3—4 извора, крайниятъ отъ които тече подъ слабъ напоръ. Извори има тамъ и въ рѣчното легло (4—5), на единъ отъ които е чешмата.

Температурата на водата на „Гьола“ е $35^{\circ}C$, на пералията — $44^{\circ}C$, на изворчето презъ рѣката — $43^{\circ}C$, а на онава надъ чешмата $34^{\circ}C$. Сега ги каптиратъ. Кота 420 м.

7. Момина баня (Солудервентъ). Изворътъ е въ гранитова скала. Той не е каптиранъ, понеже отворътъ му е на повърхността въ гранитова скала, а е покритъ и ограденъ наоколо съ зидъ за предпазване отъ приливъ на рѣчна

Fig. 2. Title page of the Journal of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences and selected pages from the article.

Fig. 3. Map of the springs visited and described by Academician Georgi Bonchev.

For some thermal water deposits, it is found that, after the initial increase in the flow rate after drilling, there is a gradual decrease, and with time the flow rate approaches the initial one before drilling (Petrov *et al.*, 1999). Examples of this are the Hisarya and Guliyna Banya deposits.

The Hisarya thermal water deposit has been known and used since ancient times. There are 20 natural springs, grouped in two zones. According to G. Bonchev, the total flow rate of the springs in 1939 was about 20 l/s. Part of the water was used in public baths (Fig. 6). In the period 1959–1963, four boreholes were drilled, and in the period 1965–1967 four more boreholes were drilled. Their depth is from 303 m to 691 m. Drilling the boreholes led to a sharp increase in the total flow rate of the mineral water, but at the same time there is a decrease in the discharge of some of the natural springs (Fig. 7). As a result of the increase in flow rate, Hisarya became a national resort with sanatoriums, spa centers and bottling plants. Over time, the total flow rate of the deposit decreased, and in 1998 the total amount measured was approximately the same as before drilling. The posi-

tive effect is that the water from the boreholes has an increased temperature.

Mineral waters from the Guliyna Banya deposit have also been used from past centuries until now (Fig. 8). Before drilling, there were two groups of 28 natural springs. Georgi Bonchev did not measure their flow rate, but only mentioned that it was high, with a water temperature of 35–37 °C.

After 1956, eight boreholes were drilled with a depth of 85 m to 500 m. Initially, the flow rate increased almost 2.5 times (and the water temperature rose to 57 °C), then gradually decreased to slightly higher than the initial flow rate. All water sources show a strong interaction with each other. Many of the natural springs greatly reduce their flow rate or dry up after drilling the boreholes, which operate on a self-flow basis (Fig. 9).

Some of the lukewarm and cold springs with mineral waters have also been the subject of additional research and drilling for mineral water (*e.g.*, Voneshta Voda, Shipkovo, Stefan Karadzhovo). According to G. Bonchev (1939), the Voneshta Voda cold mineral spring has a flow rate of 4 l/s and a temperature of 13 °C. It was captured in 1973, and

Table 1
 Thermal mineral springs visited and described by G. Bonchev

Location	T, °C	Q, l/m	Location	T, °C	Q, l/m
I. On the Sub-Balkan "diaclyse"			VI. Springs on the Rhodope Mts. "diaclyses"		
1. Burgas or Aytos springs	41.5	2000	A. On the "diaclyse" of the river Eli Dere	64	200
2. Sliven springs	45	350	B. On the "diaclyse" of the Chepino valley with N-S direction		
3. Kortenski (Banya Village) springs	22–54	400	1. At Korava	54	60
4. Gorno Panicharevo springs	48.5	240	2. Kamenitsa	68–77	670
5. Kazanlak or Ovoshnik springs	42	low	3. Velyova Banya	44	331
6. Pavel Banya	35–50	314	4. Ladzhene	53.5–60.3	356
7. Karlovska Banya	36–47.5	738	5. Chepinska Banya (Chuchura)	47–48.3	200
8. Stoletovo	34	120	C. On the Krichim "diaclyse" with N–S direction		
II. On the Srednogorie "diaclyse"			1. In the riverbed of the Vacha River	28	unknown
1. Hisar	35–74	1	2. Leskovo springs (Devin)	40	100
2. Davadzhovo	37	170	D. On the "diaclyse" of the Ladzhene River (Devin area)		
5. Knyazhevo springs	22.2–36.8	240	1. Beden	51–60	90.8
6. Bankya springs	32–37.2	1210	E. On the "diaclyse" of the Malka Arda River		
5. Strelcha springs	39.8	200	1. Ladzhenska Banya	40	90
6. Butenska Banya (Panagyurishte)	41–44	1800	F. On the "diaclyse" of the Chaya River		
7. Momina Banya (Soludervent)	65.4	920	1. Narechen springs	30	197
8. Pchelin Banya	72.5	670	G. The "diaclyse" around Ayda (Eastern slopes of the Rhodope Mountains)		
9. Dolna Banya springs	52.3	135	1. Haskovo or Susame springs	54–58	5350
III. On the "diaclyse" of the northern slopes of the Rhodope Mountains			H. The "diaclyse" on the Kanina River		
1. Kostenets springs	42.2	261	1. Nevrokop springs	41	942
2. Saranovsko – Malo-Belovski (baths)	23.5–25	2410	VII. On the "diaclyses" around and in the Mesta River		
3. Varvara springs	33–66	560	1. Guliyna Banya Village	35–37	high, not measured
IV. On the "diaclyse" of the northern slopes of Vitosha – Lyulin			2. Eleshnitsa	36–56	800
1. Pancharevo springs	48	> 158	3. Dobrinishte	38–40	900
2. Sofia city springs	47	660–900	4. Filipovo springs (Nevrokop)		
3. Ovcha Kupel springs	32	280	5. Banichan springs (Nevrokop)		
4. Gorna Banya springs	19.8–41.5	205	VIII. On the "diaclyse" of the Struma River		
2. Saparevo springs	45.6–86	100	1. Gorna Dzhumaya springs	35–55	615
3. Kadin Bridge springs	low T	260	2. Simitli springs	42–60	590
7. Zheleznitsa springs	22–32.5	478	3. Kresna springs	49–62	122
8. Kladnitsa springs	26.6–27.5	236	4. Sveti Vrach springs	61–83	461
V. On the "diaclyse" in the northern slopes of Rila and Osogovo			5. Marikostinovo (Levunovo) springs	55–57	563
1. Belchin springs	38.6	478	6. Shirbanovo springs	different	unknown
2. Saparevo springs	45.6–86	100	IX. On the "diaclyse" of the steep Balkan in Berkovitsa area		
3. Kadin Bridge springs	low T	260	1. Varshets springs	32.2–36.5	320
4. Kyustendil springs	65–75.5	1838	X. Stara Zagora springs (Sulishki)		
				45.2	570

Table 2
Lukewarm and cold springs with mineralized waters visited and described by G. Bonchev

1	Pavel Banya – Gyolchinata, Stublata and Cheshmata	29	Vladislavtsi and Nesla villages, Sofia
2	Varshets – south of the Zanozhene–Spanchevtsi road	30	Buchino Dervent Village, Sofia
3	Breznik spring in Leskov Dol	31	Zhivkovo Village, Ihtiman
4	Voneshta Voda, Voynezha Village	32	Novo Selo Village, Konyavska Planina Mt
5	Debelets Village, Veliko Tarnovo area	33	Kladnitsa Village springs
6	Manoya Village, Veliko Tarnovo area	34	Merichleri Village
7	Bebrovo Village – “Vontyo”, Elena area	35	Yarlovo Village, Tran area
8	Kapinovo Village, Veliko Tarnovo area	36	Spring Tekiry, Chirpan area
9	Tryavna	37	Dolni Rakovets Village
10	Ganchovets Village, Dryanovo	38	Kotel – The “gunpowder” spring
11	Tapanari Village, Dryanovo	39	Sindel Village, Varna area
12	Velko Tarnovo – Derventya	40	Tutrakantsi Village, Provadia area
13	Shipkovo Village, Troyan area	41	Mirovo Station, Provadiya area
14	Kalkovo Village, Samokov area	42	Plazhata, Provadiya area
15	Sungulari Village – Ichmeto, Karnobat	43	Bratsigovo
16	Sungulari Village – Teketo, Karnobat	44	Sheitanovo Village, Asenovgrad area
17	Zavet Village, Karnobat area	45	Slivek Village, Lovech area
18	Ichme Vakiv Village, Aytos area	46	Radingrad Village, Razgrad area
19	Ustovo Village, Aytos	47	Oshtava Village, Sveti Vrach
20	Yablechevo Village, Aytos	48	Osenovo Village, Blagoevgrad area
21	Bata Village, Pomorie area	49	East Shivachevo Village, Nova Zagora
22	Gyueshevo Village, Kyustendil area	50	Bukovo Village, Stara Zagora
23	Mahalata Village, Pleven area	51	Razdelna Village, artesian well
24	Tersa Dere, Haskovo area	52	Etropole – “thrills”
25	Stefan Karadzhovo, Elhovo	53	Yambol mineral water
26	Gorno Uyno Village, Kyustendil area	54	Zlatograd
27	Zheravna Village, Kotel area	55	Mrzevo Village, Malko Tarnovo area
28	Belopoptsi Village (Novo Selo)	56	Neshkovtsi, Troyan area

Fig. 4. Rupite – location of the springs in the 1930s and the boreholes in 2022.

Fig. 5. Eruption of hot water from a borehole at Sapareva Banya (2022) (photo: Miloslava Angelova).

Fig. 8. Murtina Banya, 17th century (Guliyna Banya thermal water deposit) (picture source: <http://www.bulgariatravel.tv>).

Fig. 6. Fountain from a captured spring "Momina salza" (picture source: <https://visithisarya.com>).

Fig. 9. Changes in the flow rate of the Guliyna Banya deposit.

Fig. 7. Change in the total flow rate of the Hisar mineral water deposit (Hristov *et al.*, 2015).

the water is used after heating. Drilled boreholes, one of which with a depth of 450 m, did not find warm waters.

During his visit to the spring near the village of Shipkovo, G. Bonchev measured a flow rate of 3.2 l/s and a temperature of 23 °C. In 1964–1966, three boreholes with depths of 174 m, 224 m and 216 m were drilled adjacent to the natural mineral spring. The last borehole finds water different in composition from that of the spring. In 1982–1984, three new boreholes were drilled in the Shipkovo area, two of which were 1031 m and 1339 m deep and found mineral waters from deep-lying dolomites. The water temperature is 18–37 °C and the resources of the mineral water deposit are estimated at more than 60 l/s.

A comparison of the springs visited by G. Bonchev with more up-to-date information based on detailed hydrogeological mappings shows that

the number of new water sources is not so large. It is of interest for future research to establish whether all the sources registered by Georgi Bonchev still exist.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the information about the springs in Bulgaria, published in 1939 by Academician G. Bonchev, allows getting a real idea of the discharge of thermal and mineral waters in Bulgaria before the serious anthropogenic intervention in the second half of the 20th century, related to the drilling of boreholes. It was found that, for some mineral water deposits, there is an increase in the flow rate and temperature of the thermal water, which has allowed the construction of modern balneological and spa resorts. For the other deposits, there is a temporary effect, a sharp increase in the discharge, which gradually decreases over time, approaching the initial values. In the future, it is necessary to visit

the 290 karst springs located by G. Bonchev and to assess their current condition, in order to assess the impact of changes in the hydrogeological conditions for a period of more than 80 years. These expected results, together with the conclusions drawn for the thermal and mineral waters, confirm the importance of Academician Georgi Bonchev's work for Bulgarian hydrogeology.

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